

Gravimetric Determination and Separation of Alkaline-Earth Metals with N-*p*-Chlorophenylcinnamohydroxamic Acid

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A gravimetric method for determination and separation of beryllium, magnesium, calcium and barium with N-*p*-chlorophenylcinnamohydroxamic acid is described. The interference of several metal ions has been eliminated either by judicious choice of masking agents or by adjustment of pH. The complexes show the structure $M(C_{15}H_{11}NO_2Cl)_2$.

HYDROXAMIC acids being bidentate ligands fulfill the basic requirement for complex formation¹⁻³.

The metal complexes are insoluble in water which can form the basis of gravimetric estimation of metals in microgram quantities⁴. A few data are available on the estimation of beryllium, magnesium and barium⁵⁻⁹ but not calcium. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to separate Be, Mg, Ca and Ba from each other and estimate them in microgram quantities in presence of several diverse ions.

Experimental

All the chemicals used are of A.R. or G.R. grades (B.D.H. and E. Merck) unless otherwise specified.

N-*p*-Chlorophenylcinnamohydroxamic acid was synthesised as described elsewhere¹⁰ and 0.2% w/v solution in ethanol was used for the precipitation of metal ions.

The requisite amounts of beryllium sulphate ($BeSO_4 \cdot 4H_2O$), magnesium sulphate ($MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$), calcium nitrate ($Ca(NO_3)_2 \cdot H_2O$) and barium chloride ($BaCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$) were dissolved in distilled water to obtain 0.01 M solutions. The solutions were standardized volumetrically¹¹. Further dilutions are made as and when required.

Gravimetric determination of alkaline-earth metals :

Ten ml 0.01 M metal ion solution (Be, Mg, Ca or Ba) and 300 ml distilled water were taken in a 500 ml beaker and heated to 60-65° on a water bath. The pH of the solution was adjusted with 0.1 M ammonium hydroxide and 0.1 M hydrochloric acid. 20-25 ml reagent solution (0.2% ethanolic) was added slowly with constant stirring till complete precipitation was obtained and the mixture digested on a water bath for 20 min. The granular light yellow

precipitates were filtered hot through a dry tared sintered glass crucible (G-4). The precipitates were then washed with hot water and 40% v/v ethanol-water mixture, dried at 110° for 3-4 hr and weighed as $(C_{15}H_{11}NO_2Cl)_2M$.

Separation of Be, Mg, Ca and Ba from common metal ions :

(i) *Using masking agents* : Into 10 ml alkaline earth solution (0.01 M) known amount of desired foreign metal ions were added and diluted to 500 ml. The pH was adjusted, 10 ml 1% KCN solution was added, the contents heated to 60° and the reagent solution added dropwise with constant stirring. The complex thus formed was allowed to stand for about 30 min on a water bath. It was filtered, washed, dried and weighed as before. Be, Mg, Ca and Ba could be separated from and determined in presence of Ag^+ , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Fe^{2+} and Ga^{3+} . Alkaline earth could be separated from Pb^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , Sb^{3+} , Sn^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , Zr^{4+} , Ti^{4+} , V^{5+} and Mo^{6+} with 10 ml 1% citrate and oxalate instead of KCN solution. Alkaline earth could also be separated from Al^{3+} , V^{5+} and Mo^{6+} , and Pb^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , Sb^{3+} , Bi^{3+} , Zr^{4+} , Ti^{4+} , La^{3+} , Ce^{3+} , Pr^{3+} and Nd^{3+} using Mg-EDTA and NTA as masking agents, respectively.

(ii) *By adjusting the pH* : 10 ml solution of alkaline earth (0.01 M) were diluted to 500 ml and mixed with foreign metal ions. Ag^+ , Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Th^{4+} and U^{6+} were precipitated below pH 5.5 using excess of reagent. The precipitate was filtered, washed and the alkaline earth was reprecipitated from the mother liquor by adjusting the respective pH.

Separation from alkaline earth : Mg, Ca, and Ba could be determined in presence of Be^{2+} using NaF as masking agent. The separation of Be, Ca, Mg and Ba could also be made by adjustment of the respective pH of precipitation.

Results and Discussion

The pH of precipitation for various alkaline earth metals with N-*p*-chlorophenylcinnamohydroxamic acid alongwith the elemental analyses is given in Table 1.

 TABLE 1—OPTIMUM pH FOR THE PRECIPITATION OF ALKALINE EARTHS WITH N-*p*-CHLOROPHENYL-CINNAMOHYDROXAMIC ACID

Metal	pH of precipitation	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
		O	H	N	M
1. Be ²⁺	7.2-8.0	64.94 (64.99)	3.98 (4.00)	5.03 (5.05)	1.64 (1.63)
2. Mg ²⁺	8.0-8.5	63.20 (63.25)	3.91 (3.89)	4.90 (4.92)	4.25 (4.27)
3. Ca ²⁺	9.5-10.2	61.39 (61.53)	3.81 (3.79)	4.82 (4.78)	6.83 (6.85)
4. Ba ²⁺	3.0-3.5	52.59 (52.78)	3.30 (3.25)	4.13 (4.10)	20.08 (20.12)

Gravimetric determination of beryllium :

The analytical data on the gravimetric determination of beryllium are given in Table 2. The complex is light yellow in colour and is soluble in dioxane. It decomposes when treated with excess perchloric or nitric acid. The analytical results have confirmed the composition of the complex as (C₁₅H₁₁NO₂Cl)₂Be. The data on the separation and determination of beryllium are given in Table 3.

The precipitation of beryllium-N-*p*-chlorophenylcinnamohydroxamate appeared above pH 7.0 and precipitation is complete at pH 7.2-8.0. Above pH 8.0 low results are obtained. Complete precipitation of beryllium required at least 2.5-3.0 times the theoretical amount of reagent.

Gravimetric determination of magnesium :

The analytical data on the gravimetric determination of magnesium are given in Table 4. The complex is yellowish white in colour and is soluble in dioxane, chloroform, etc. It decomposes when treated with perchloric or nitric acid. The complex is stable upto 200-250°. The analytical results showed that the complex corresponds to the formula (C₁₅H₁₁NO₂Cl)₂Mg.

 TABLE 2—GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF BERYLLIUM WITH N-*p*-CHLOROPHENYL-CINNAMOHYDROXAMIC ACID

Beryllium taken mg	Found		Error
	Complex mg	Beryllium mg	
0.20	12.30	0.20	—
2.00	123.04	2.00	—
5.00	308.23	5.01	-0.01
7.50	462.65	7.52	-0.02
10.00	613.99	9.98	+0.02
12.50	768.41	12.49	+0.01
15.00	922.83	15.00	—
20.00	1230.44	19.99	+0.01

Relative standard deviation = 0.45%

 TABLE 3—SEPARATION AND GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF BERYLLIUM FROM OTHER METAL IONS WITH N-*p*-CHLOROPHENYL-CINNAMOHYDROXAMIC ACID Beryllium = 5 mg

Diverse ions mg	Masking agent	Beryllium found mg
Ag ⁺ (50)	cyanide ; a	5.02
Mn ²⁺ (75)	cyanide	5.01
Zn ²⁺ (75)	cyanide ; a	5.02
Cd ²⁺ (75)	cyanide ; a	5.03
Hg ²⁺ (100)	cyanide	5.00
Cu ²⁺ (100)	cyanide ; a	4.98
Fe ²⁺ (80)	cyanide	4.97
Ga ²⁺ (80)	cyanide	4.99
Pb ²⁺ (80)	cit+ox ; NTA ; a	4.99
Pd ²⁺ (80)	cit+ox ; NTA	5.01
Sb ²⁺ (80)	cit+ox	5.01
Sn ²⁺ (100)	cit+ox ; NTA	5.00
Bi ²⁺ (100)	cit+ox ; NTA	5.00
Zr ⁴⁺ (100)	cit+ox ; NTA	5.01
Al ³⁺ (80)	Mg-EDTA ; a	5.02
V ⁵⁺ (80)	Mg-EDTA	5.00
Mo ⁶⁺ (100)	Mg-EDTA	4.99
Ti ⁴⁺ (80)	NTA	4.99
Rare earths (80)	NTA	5.00
Th ⁴⁺ (80)	a	5.00
U ⁶⁺ (80)	a	5.00
Ba ²⁺ (80)	a	5.00
Ca ²⁺ (80)	a	5.00
Mg ²⁺ (80)	a	5.02

cit=Citrate ; ox =Oxalate ; NTA =Nitrilotriacetate ; a =Adjusting the pH.

 TABLE 4—GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF MAGNESIUM WITH N-*p*-CHLOROPHENYL-CINNAMOHYDROXAMIC ACID

Magnesium taken mg	Found		Error
	Complex mg	Magnesium mg	
0.50	11.48	0.49	+0.01
2.00	47.10	2.01	-0.01
3.00	70.30	3.00	—
5.00	117.15	5.00	—
7.00	163.77	6.99	+0.01
10.00	233.87	9.99	+0.01
15.00	351.74	15.02	-0.02
20.00	468.91	20.02	-0.02

Relative standard deviation = 0.25%

The data on the separation and gravimetric determination of magnesium are given in Table 5.

The precipitate of magnesium-N-*p*-chlorophenylcinnamohydroxamate appears at pH 8.0-8.5. Above pH 8.5 the precipitate gets dissolved while below pH 8.0 it gives turbidity only.

Gravimetric determination of calcium :

The analytical data on the gravimetric determination of calcium are given in Table 6. The complex is white in colour and stable in dioxane, chloroform, ethyl methyl ketone. It decomposes when treated with perchloric or nitric acid. The analytical results confirmed the composition of the complex as (C₁₅H₁₁NO₂Cl)₂Ca.

TABLE 5—SEPARATION AND GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF MAGNESIUM FROM OTHER METAL IONS WITH N-P-CHLOROPHENYLCINNAMOHYDROXAMIC ACID

Diverse ions mg	Magnesium=10 mg	
	Masking agent	Magnesium found mg
Ag ⁺ (50)	cyanide ; a	10.00
Mn ²⁺ (75)	cyanide	10.00
Zn ²⁺ (75)	cyanide ; a	10.02
Cd ²⁺ (75)	cyanide ; a	10.01
Hg ²⁺ (100)	cyanide	9.98
Cu ²⁺ (100)	cyanide ; a	10.01
Fe ²⁺ (80)	cyanide	9.98
Ga ³⁺ (80)	cyanide	10.02
Pb ²⁺ (80)	cit+ox ; NTA ; a	10.00
Pd ²⁺ (80)	cit+ox ; NTA	10.01
V ⁵⁺ (80)	cit+ox	10.02
Mo ⁶⁺ (100)	cit+ox	10.01
Sb ³⁺ (80)	cit+ox ; iodate	10.01
Sn ²⁺ (80)	cit+ox ; NTA	9.98
Bi ³⁺ (100)	cit+ox ; NTA	9.98
Zr ⁴⁺ (100)	cit+ox ; NTA	9.98
Ti ⁴⁺ (100)	cit+ox ; NTA	10.01
Al ³⁺ (80)	F ; a	10.02
Be ²⁺ (80)	F	10.00
Rare earths (80)	NTA	10.00
Ba ²⁺ (80)	a	10.01
Sr ²⁺ (80)	a	10.02
Th ⁴⁺ (80)	a	10.00
U ⁶⁺ (80)	a	9.99
Ca ²⁺ (80)	a+SPT	10.01

cit=Citrate ; ox=Oxalate ; NTA=Nitrilotriacetate ;
a=Adjusting the pH ; SPT=Sodium potassium tartrate.

TABLE 7—SEPARATION AND GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF CALCIUM FROM OTHER METAL IONS WITH N-P-CHLOROPHENYLCINNAMOHYDROXAMIC ACID

Diverse ions mg	Calcium=10 mg	
	Masking agent	Calcium found mg
Ag ⁺ (50)	cyanide ; a	10.01
Mn ²⁺ (75)	cyanide	10.02
Zn ²⁺ (75)	cyanide ; a	10.02
Cd ²⁺ (75)	cyanide ; a	10.01
Hg ²⁺ (100)	cyanide	10.01
Cu ²⁺ (100)	cyanide ; a	10.01
Fe ²⁺ (80)	cyanide	10.00
Ga ³⁺ (80)	cyanide	10.00
Pb ²⁺ (80)	cit+tart ; NTA ; a	9.98
Pd ²⁺ (80)	cit+tart ; NTA	9.98
V ⁵⁺ (80)	cit+tart	9.99
Mo ⁶⁺ (100)	cit+tart	9.98
Sb ³⁺ (80)	cit+tart ; iodate	10.01
Sn ²⁺ (100)	cit+tart ; NTA	10.01
Bi ³⁺ (100)	cit+tart ; NTA	10.01
Zr ⁴⁺ (100)	cit+tart ; NTA	10.00
Ti ⁴⁺ (80)	cit+tart ; NTA	10.01
Al ³⁺ (80)	F ; a	10.2
Be ²⁺ (80)	F	9.98
Rare earths (100)	NTA	10.00
Ba ²⁺ (80)	a	10.02
Sr ²⁺ (80)	a	10.02
Th ⁴⁺ (80)	a	9.99
U ⁶⁺	a	10.02

cit=Citrate ; tart=Tartrate ; F=Fluoride ; NTA=Nitrilotriacetate ; a=Adjusting the pH.

TABLE 6—GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF CALCIUM WITH N-P-CHLOROPHENYLCINNAMOHYDROXAMIC ACID

Calcium taken mg	Found		Error
	Complex mg	Calcium mg	
2.00	29.29	2.00	—
4.00	58.43	4.00	—
6.00	87.79	6.01	-0.01
7.50	109.28	7.48	+0.02
10.00	145.80	9.98	+0.02
15.00	218.68	14.97	+0.03
20.00	292.38	20.02	-0.2

Relative standard deviation=0.5%

The data on separation of calcium from common metal ions are given in Table 7.

10 ml of 0.1 M sodium nitrate was most adequate for the quantitative determination of calcium (10 mg). An excess of sodium nitrate gives lower results.

The experimental studies of the determination of calcium in solution of different pH values with all other factors identical reveal that precipitation commences at pH 9.5 and is quantitative in the pH range 9.5-10.2.

Gravimetric determination of barium :

The analytical data on the gravimetric determination of barium are given in Table 8. The com-

TABLE 8—GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF BARIUM WITH N-P-CHLOROPHENYLCINNAMOHYDROXAMIC ACID

Barium taken mg	Found		Error
	Complex mg	Barium mg	
2.00	9.98	1.99	+0.01
4.00	19.79	3.98	+0.02
5.00	24.91	5.01	-0.01
7.50	37.33	7.51	-0.01
10.00	49.66	9.99	+0.01
12.00	59.56	11.98	+0.02
15.00	74.47	14.98	+0.02

Relative standard deviation=0.38%

plex is fairly soluble in dioxane, ethanol and chloroform but sparingly soluble in ether, carbon tetrachloride and glacial acetic acid. It decomposes when treated with perchloric, sulphuric or nitric acid. The analytical results indicate the composition of the complex as (C₁₅H₁₅NO₂Cl)₂Ba.

The data on the separation and determination of barium are given in Table 9.

Separation and gravimetric determination of barium in solutions of different pH with all other factors identical revealed that these can be done best in the pH range 3.0-3.5.

TABLE 9—SEPARATION AND GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF BARIUM FROM OTHER METAL IONS WITH N-p-CHLOROPHENYL CINNAMOHYDROXAMIC ACID

Diverse ions mg	Barium = 7.5 mg Masking agent	Barium found mg
Ag ⁺ (50)	cyanide	7.48
Mn ²⁺ (75)	cyanide	7.49
Cu ²⁺ (100)	cyanide ; a	7.50
Ni ²⁺ (75)	cyanide	7.52
Cd ²⁺ (75)	cyanide ; a	7.48
Zn ²⁺ (75)	cyanide	7.51
Hg ²⁺ (100)	cyanide ; a	7.47
Pd ²⁺ (80)	cyanide	7.48
V ⁵⁺ (80)	cyanide	7.51
Be ²⁺ (80)	cit + ox	7.51
Ga ³⁺ (80)	cit + ox	7.52
Sb ³⁺ (80)	cit + ox	7.51
Mg ²⁺ (80)	cit + ox ; a	7.49
Ca ²⁺ (80)	cit + ox ; a	7.49
As ³⁺ (80)	cit + ox	7.50
Bi ³⁺ (100)	cit + ox	7.50
Ti ⁴⁺ (80)	cit + ox	7.50
Zr ⁴⁺ (100)	cit + ox	7.51
UO ₂ ²⁺ (80)	Mg-EDTA	7.50
Mo ⁶⁺ (100)	Mg-EDTA	7.50
Rare earths (100)	a	7.49

cit=Citrate ; ox = Oxalate ; a = Adjusting the pH.

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